

In recent years, coal tar and kerosene oil at 1:2 have been blended with urea and margosa cake for better adherence. The combination has helped inhibit nitrification and reduce nitrogen loss through NO_3 leaching and denitrification. It is used as a basal application to save the cost of topdressing, and can be used in split applications where topdressing is difficult because of waterlogging.

A randomized block design with 4 replications was used during the 1980 rainy season to evaluate margosa-urea application of suboptimum nitrogen levels (50 kg N/ha) in fields. Soil was silty

clay loam, pH 7.8, 1.38% organic carbon, with 50 kg available P/ha and 162 available K/ha. A treatment of near optimum nitrogen (100 kg N/ha) was included for comparison. The nursery was sown 6 June and the crop harvested 23 October.

Urea blended with 15% margosa powder alone, or with coal tar and kerosene oil, yielded 5.3 t/ha — comparable to yield with urea best split (5.1 t/ha) — and gave the highest grain yield response (42 kg grain/kg N) (see table). Urea coated with coal tar and kerosene oil was equally effective. Margosa cake

showed no advantage over split-applied urea in areas where topdressing can be practiced.

Margosa application may hold promise for fields where water cannot be drained to allow topdressing. In such situations, fertilizer is applied as a single basal application. Urea blended with margosa gave 0.6 t/ha extra grain yield over single application, saving about 20% nitrogen at little extra cost (US\$4-5) in fields where topdressing could not be used because of poor drainage. *R*

Germination of seed from parent crop varieties irrigated with saline and nonsaline water

S. K. Datta, and S. K. De, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

Seven photoperiod-sensitive winter rice varieties were grown during wet season in nonsaline (control) and saline irrigated plots at the Salt Paddy Research Sub-station, Gosaba, West Bengal. The soils are silty clay loam.

Nonsaline plots were irrigated with fresh water (pH 6.5-7.6, EC 0.8-1.1 mmho/cm) from a rainfed tank. Saline plots were irrigated with saline water (pH 5.8-6.0, EC 8.0-12.8 mmho/cm) from the Vidya River, which is directly connected with the Bay of Bengal. Irrigation water salinity was recorded at 15-day intervals throughout the growing season.

Seeds harvested in November-December were thoroughly dried, cleaned, and stored in cloth bags. Seed viability was monitored for 12 months.

Seeds collected from both saline and nonsaline plots showed varying dormancies. In general, seeds from saline irrigated plots were poorer in viability retention (see figure). Germination one month after harvest was remarkably lower in salt-affected seeds than in the control, irrespective of variety, indicating the inhibitory effect of salinity on the crop. Viability of salt-affected seeds was highest in April and May, then gradually diminished.

Math variety was an exception. Its

viability gradually increased until July. Hamilton showed similar viability. Seeds of the five other varieties from saline irrigated plots rapidly lost viability after 4 months. Seeds from nonsaline plots retained over 90% germination capacity for more than 7 months.

A considerable number of seeds of the five other varieties were abnormal, with grain sterility and low grain-filling. Grain size was also reduced.

Monthly changes in germination of seeds of 7 rice varieties in saline and nonsaline irrigated plots. West Bengal, India.

Spacing and plant population for transplanted rice in alkali soil of eastern Uttar Pradesh

T. N. Singh, Crop Physiology Department, N. D. University of Agriculture & Technology, Faizabad (U.P.), India

Soil alkalinity is a major constraint to transplanted rice production in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Patchy plant growth, thin plant population, restricted tiller production, and decreased grain formation cause low yield in alkali (sodic) soils.

An experiment in July 1976 determined optimum plant density and population for increased rice production in alkali soils. Plants were tested in 3 replications at 10-, 15-, and 20-cm spacing and rates of 2, 3, 4, and 5 seedlings/hill.

Because natural soil pH was 10.3, gypsum at 6 and 12 t/ha was applied to different subplots with 3 replications 1 week before transplanting to test soil potential under partially and well-reclaimed conditions. An additional 120 kg N/ha, 50 kg P_2O_5 /ha, and 40 kg ZnSO_4 /ha were applied to all plots.

The experiment was repeated in the same plots using medium-duration variety Jaya transplanted during July 1977 and 1978.

In partially reclaimed soil, narrow spacing yields were highest, with yields increasing as plant populations per hill increased (see table). Maximum yields of 2.1, 5.5, and 5.3 t/ha during 1976, 1977, and 1978 were at 10-cm spacing and 5 seedling/hill.

In well-reclaimed soil neither 10-cm nor 20-cm spacings yielded higher. During 1976 highest yield was at 15-cm spacing and 5 seedlings/ hill. Although general yield levels increased with plant populations and with soil improvement,

the difference in yield between the 2 best treatments (4 and 5 seedlings/ hill) narrowed to become statistically equal. Maximum grain yields of 6.5 and 6.6 t/ha during 1977 and 1978 were at 15-cm spacing and 4 seedlings/hill. 🌾

Effect of spacing and plant population (2, 3,4, and 5 seedlings/hill) on rice yield in partially and well-reclaimed alkali soils of Kumarganj (Faizabad), India.

Spacing (cm)	Gypsum ^a (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)			
		2	3	4	5
<i>Pusa 2-21 (1976)</i>					
10	6	1.2	1.5	1.6	2.1
	12	1.2	1.6	1.8	2.2
15	6	1.0	1.3	1.7	2.1
	12	1.6	2.1	3.1	3.8
20	6	0.8	1.1	1.4	1.7
	12	1.5	1.9	2.2	2.7
LSD (0.05)		0.3			
<i>Java (1977)</i>					
10	6	4.3	4.7	5.1	5.5
	12	5.5	6.0	5.3	4.8
15	6	3.8	4.2	4.7	5.2
	12	5.1	5.5	6.5	6.3
20	6	3.5	3.9	4.3	4.6
	12	5.0	5.3	5.9	6.2
LSD (0.05)		0.5			
<i>Jaya (1978)</i>					
10	6	4.1	4.5	5.0	5.3
	12	5.3	5.6	5.4	4.8
15	6	3.6	4.0	4.5	4.9
	12	5.2	5.8	6.6	6.4
20	6	3.5	3.7	4.1	4.5
	12	4.9	5.3	5.7	6.1
LSD (0.05)		0.4			

^aGypsum was applied only once, in 1976.

Optimum spacing and nitrogen for medium-duration rice

Syed Nazeer Peeran and B. V. Anandan, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Tirur 602025, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, India

A 1982 experiment during samba (July-August to November-December) at PES, Tirur, showed that Ponni and IR20 yields increased at 20 × 20 cm rice plant spacing, regardless of the level of nitrogen applied (see table). 🌾

Effect of nitrogen levels and spacings on rice yield, Tirur, India, 1982 samba.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Ponni yield (t/ha)		IR20 yield (t/ha)	
	20 × 10 cm	20 × 20 cm	20 × 10 cm	20 × 20 cm
0	3.4	3.9	3.3	3.7
10	4.0	4.4	3.7	4.1
20	4.2	4.9	4.2	4.6
30	4.6	5.1	4.6	5.0
Mean	4.1	4.6	4.0	4.4
		CD	CD	
Nitrogen level	0.3**		0.2**	
Spacing	0.3**		0.2**	

Environment and its influence

Variations and associations in rice physiological growth parameters

S. K. Shrivastava and P. K. Saxena, Agricultural Botany Department, JNKVV, Jabalpur 482004, India

Grain productivity can be improved by using component breeding, which assumes productivity is associated with growth parameters and their heritability. Direct and indirect gene action related to productivity and growth traits should be known. This study hypothesizes level of improvement can be predicted by calculating the genetic coefficient of variation using heritability estimates.

Jaya, Kranti, JR 16-15-2, JR25-13-8, Madhuri, Garima, Ratna, Anupama, JR15-55-2, and IR36 were grown in a randomized block design with three replications at JNKVV Research Farm during July 1978-79. Growth parameters were evaluated every 2 weeks.

Physiological growth parameters among varieties varied significantly. Means of individual characteristics and the general mean also differed (Table 1). Coefficient of variation for genotype (gcv) ranged from 1.05 relative growth rate (RGR) to 25.99 leaf area ratio (LAR). Coefficient of variation for phenotype (pcv) ranged from 15.02 net assimilation rate (NAR) to 50.43 RGR. The gcv was equally higher in leaf area index (LAI) and crop growth rate (CGR), indicating the level of possible improvement.

Heritability values for all characteristics exhibited wide variations: range of 21.1 to 89.6. Heritability estimates were high for RGR followed by seed yield and leaf parameter (leaf weight ratio [LWR], LAR, and LAI). NAR and specific leaf area (SLA) had lower heritability values, reflecting environmental influence. Maximum genetic improvement was recorded for LAI and LAR

Positive, significant associations of LAI were recorded with leaf area dura-